

SHOPPERS' OPINIONS ON INFORMAL RETAIL STORES BANNER SYMBOLISM

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: This article provides a text mining analysis of customers' opinion of misspelled retail store signage using NVivo software and suggests measures for small retailers to focus on retail signage semiotics.

Design Methodology: The sample signages (5 images) were distributed online and 112 completed customer opinions were collected in the form of an open ended questionnaire along with few scaled questions and demographics questions. The sentiments behind the opinions were analyzed and keywords were extracted using NVivo software.

Findings: In general, small store signages are viewed are not at all important from the view point of majority of retailers themselves as they feel that their proximity and availability near a residential layout is most important. Though this statement is true, they lose out on opportunity largely because many other small store retailers or a mid-sized departmental store in the same area grabs the opportunity by demonstrating a host of attributes including signage to attract customers.

Research Implications: Customers though reach out small stores for their daily needs, tend to evaluate stores based on their appearance and more specifically in terms of the details showcased in the form of signages and other boards in front of the store. Therefore, it is significantly important for small store retailers to design their signages prominently loaded with sufficient store related information to attract customers, which in turn can help to retain them for the long run.

Scope for future work / Research limitations: A significant percentage (66%) of opinions drawn from the sample survey respondents depict that the signages of small stores were neutral. This in turn could mean that customers have not affixed enough weightage to the signage of small stores and therefore small retailers can use this as an opportunity to attract customers with attractive signages with good and sufficient information.

Originality/value: Being an opinion text analysis study the choice of signages were selected in random order as the study aims at understanding the response of any customer towards a small store signage in terms of what they feel about the usage of store related attributes and spellings.

Keywords: NVivo, small retail store, signage, banner

Paper type: Research paper

INTRODUCTION

In comparison to huge retail formats, India has an exponentially enormous number of small retail stores. Customers in India also do not have extremely tight buying patterns in terms of buying exclusively from a single store every time they make a purchase. Unless they have the luxury of time, they frequently rely on tiny merchants near their homes for many of their daily and weekly necessities, such as groceries, dairy products, and provisions. Customers may not expect significant branding efforts from tiny neighbouring establishments, especially when compared to huge retail formats that they may look up to for their big monthly purchases (Lee et al., 2015). Smaller establishments near people's homes, on the other hand, require a steady stream of consumers to maintain their investments and revenues. While the availability of products for daily necessities may be the top priority for such tiny retail establishments, making an attempt to attract/notify customers about the products available is equally critical (Mehta & NafisurRahman, 2020). This may be accomplished efficiently by having appropriate retail signage that can demonstrate their store brand as well as a variety of other store-related qualities such as products and services offered (Pantano, 2016).

While the organised retail sector and large shop formats take great care in designing their store signage and semiotics to attract customers in both non-digital and digital forms, the organised retail sector and large store formats take great care in designing their store signage and semiotics. Unorganized or small businesses are still less likely to use retail signage to brand themselves and attract clients. A small store's greatest effort is to display the business name and type of store, which is nevertheless capable of branding in their context (Oh & Petrie 2012). However, a large number of small-business retailers focus on the many components of signage that must be included, and they reap significant benefits in terms of client reach and exposure. However, the majority of small merchants are concerned about inaccuracies in the names/words used in signs, as well as the lack of specifics in signage (Meikle, 2013). This essay will concentrate on this topic because the concept of signage is the single most crucial or initial point of contact for a consumer looking for a specific store to meet his needs.

Small merchants focus extensively on the required merchandise and inventory-related aspects of their store, so store signage is typically overlooked (Pantano, Priporas, & Foroudi, 2019). This is evident from the fact that the majority of small businesses fall prey to certain companies who offer them free store signage that has 98 percent brand-related information and 2% space with the small business's name in one corner (Jasonet.al, 2004). Small stores, on the other hand, that are located in the vicinity of residential areas, receive the essential footfalls without the need for additional marketing efforts such as advertising, promotion, and so on, which are a significant marketing agenda for large merchants (Kim, 2017). As a result, the focus of this article is on the consumers' perceptions of the signage and semiotics seen at a few general stores, with no specific restrictions drawn in terms of geography, kind, or business size.

For text analysis, a sample of small business signage and semiotics were chosen at random and distributed to customers who had previously used the services of small stores in their area. Because this is an opinion text analysis study, the signages were chosen at random. The goal is to learn how customers react to tiny store signpost and how they feel about the

use of store-related features and spellings. The example signages (5 images) were distributed online, and 46 completed customer evaluations were collected via an open ended questionnaire with a few scaled questions and demographics questions. NVivo software was used to assess the attitudes behind the opinions and extract keywords (Durian, 2002).

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Users' feedback on each of the five example signpost graphics was compiled into a text file and analysed. NVivo software (Hilal&Alabri, 2013) and MS Excel were used to create the following results.

According to the findings, 63 percent of customer opinions on all five signs were neutral, indicating that customers had no substantial expectations for the signs employed by small businesses. However, customers place a high value on adequate signage space and spellings in tiny establishments, with a total of 29% of evaluations being negative. It's also worth noting that just 9% of thoughts on small business signs are positive, owing to factors such as ignorance, lack of understanding, and so on among local retail chains.

Keyword extraction

The terms – ignorance, spelling, language, and proficiency – appear to have a substantial high frequency of mentions throughout the full opinion text. This indicates that small-business owners are unaware of signage errors; therefore, they should pay special attention to spelling and phrasing in their signage. The keywords – mistakes, English, quality, and so on – have been mentioned a fair amount, and these keywords are vital factors to make when designing tiny store signages.

The keywords language, spelling, and competency have a significant relationship with the other keywords extracted, and they have been mentioned frequently in conjunction with the keywords ignorance, sign board, and service. As a result, it's clear that businesses haven't given proper grammar and spelling in their signage any thought.

Store signage attributes analysis:

According to their sample opinions, small store retailers have a plethora of chances to showcase their store features in order to attract clients. On a scale of 1 to 5, the attributes of products/services offered, price of products/services, uniqueness of the store, prominence and visibility of the store name, images of products/services, and correctness of information including spellings and contact details received an average score of 4.8, 4.7, 4.6, 4.5, 4.4, and 4.2, respectively. This means that small business owners must convert their signs into a permanent promotional tool that includes the majority of information about their store and services.

RECOMMENDATIONS

A high percentage (63%) of the opinions gathered from the sample survey respondents indicated that small store signage was neutral. This could indicate that buyers haven't given tiny store signage enough weight, and small retailers can take advantage of this by attracting

customers with appealing signage that provides good and necessary information. The keywords language, proficiency, spellings, blunders, and ignorance are frequently utilised in the majority of the sample respondents' opinion assessments to emphasise the importance of proper grammar and signage words. While major retailers can take use of digital signage and multi-modal advertising (Kellaris&Machleit, 2016), small businesses cannot afford such sophisticated and pricey techniques. As a result, paying close attention to the smallest things, such as spelling, is a key factor in enticing people to the company.

Many of the sample respondents noted the keyword - the retailer's lack of knowledge of the spellings and terms used in the signs. It is critical for small-business owners to seek advice from close associates who are fluent in English. Words and traits to be mentioned in store signs might be written down by merchants or customers themselves. According to the sample data, the attributes of products/services offered, uniqueness of the store, store name, spellings, and so on are mandatory factors, and customers pay close attention to the above features (Lee et al., 2015). As a result, small merchants should not overlook these features in their signs and should make extensive use of their signage to inform shoppers about their distinctive products. This may be the need of the hour for small store retailers, rather than giving the opportunity to brands who provide them with free signage with their brand ads, where the small store retailer loses the opportunity to display his or her store's features to customers. Small store signage is generally seen as unimportant by the majority of retailers, who believe that their closeness and availability near a residential layout is the most significant factor. Despite the fact that this statement is correct, they miss out on an opportunity since many other small store retailers or a mid-sized departmental store in the same location seizes the opportunity by showing a variety of features, including signage, to attract clients (Andersen, 1997). As a result, unstructured and/or small-store businesses must place a strong emphasis on their signage, which serves as the initial point of interest for customers walking down to the store.

CONCLUSION

Small-store retailers in India operate like a one-man operation, with the shopkeeper overseeing inventory, transportation, sales, and budgeting on a daily basis. Because of the scope of their activity, they may overlook the probable degrees of branding and promotion required to showcase their stores in the face of competition from other small store merchants and organised retailers of medium or large scale in their geographic area. However, simple attempts of advertising, though not dynamic, but static in the form of store signs, are significant to highlight from the standpoint of customers. Customers who visit these tiny establishments for their daily necessities also prefer to judge them based on their look, particularly the details shown in the form of signage and other boards in front of the store. As a result, it is critical for small-business owners to design signage that is prominently displayed and has adequate store-related information in order to attract customers and maintain them over time.

REFERENCES

- Durian, D. (2002). "Corpus-based text analysis from a qualitative perspective: A closer look at NVivo". *Style*, 36(4), 738-742. DOI : <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.5325/style.36.4.738>
- Jason, L. A., Pokorny, S. B., Mikulski, K., & Schoeny, M. E. (2004). "Assessing storefront tobacco advertising after the billboard ban". *Evaluation and the Health Professions*. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1177/0163278703261211>
- Hilal, A. H., & Alabri, S. S. (2013). "Using NVivo for data analysis in qualitative research". *International interdisciplinary journal of education*, 2(2), 181-186. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.12816/0002914>
- Kellaris, J. J., & Machleit, K. A. (2016). "Signage as Marketing Communication: A Conceptual Model and Research Propositions". *Interdisciplinary Journal of Signage and Wayfinding*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15763/issn.2470-9670.2016.v1.i1.a4>
- Kim, S. (2017). "Analysis of shop sign colors in Joong-Gu, Seoul — Nadulgage and convenience stores". *Journal of Asian Architecture and Building Engineering*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3130/jaabe.16.479>
- Lee, H. K., Yoon, S. Y., Lee, J. Y., Kim, H. Bin, Kwona, H. J., Kang, H. J., ... Jun, D. G. (2015). "The effects of sale signs on consumer intentions to visit a store". *Journal of Global Fashion Marketing*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/20932685.2014.971495>
- Mehta, V., & Nafisur Rahman, M. (2020). "Signage Form and Character: a window to neighborhood visual identity". *Interdisciplinary Journal of Signage and Wayfinding*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15763/issn.2470-9670.2020.v4.i1.a59>
- Meikle, J. L. (2013). "Signs, Streets, and Storefronts: A History of Architecture and Graphics Along America's Commercial Corridors by Martin Treu". *Technology and Culture*. Volume 54, Number 3, July 2013 pp. 672-674, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1353/tech.2013.0089>
- Oh, H., & Petrie, J. (2012). "How do storefront window displays influence entering decisions of clothing stores?". *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, [Volume 19, Issue 1](#), DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2011.08.003>
- Pantano, E. (2016). "Engaging consumer through the storefront: Evidences from integrating interactive technologies". *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*. [Volume 28](#), January 2016, Pages 149-154, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2015.09.007>
- Pantano, E., Priporas, C. V., & Foroudi, P. (2019). "Innovation starts at the storefront: Modelling consumer behaviour towards storefront windows enriched with innovative technologies". *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJRDM-07-2018-0120>